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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8372440>**ARTICLE INFO**

Qabul qilindi: 18-September 2023 yil

Ma'qullandi: 20-September 2023 yil

Nashr qilindi: 23-September 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

flavoring agent, gallic acid, ellagic acid, oxymethylantraquinone, resin, isotin, theobromine, parenchyma, cambium, pyrogallol, phlobafen, lubtolasi

ABSTRACT

Today, in medicine, treatment with products obtained from natural plants is widely established, among which the important role of plants containing food additives.

Relevance of the topic: Figs from the mulberry family, a tree or shrub up to 10 m high - Mogaseae. The leaves are large, trihedral, heart-shaped-toothed, 8-15 cm long, 6-8 cm wide. There are a lot of types of figs found in the countries of the Mediterranean, Central Asia, Iran, Transcaucasia. More than 600 varieties are known in the world, which differ from each other in size, color, taste and fruit ripening time. The most popular figs are Dalmatian, Spanish, French, Californian, American and others. Figs live 150-200 years. Figs are common in the republics of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Chemical composition. Fig leaves contain a natural complex of coumarins (0.45%), in which psoralen (0.28-0.498%) and bergapten are in the lead. The content of coumarins in the organs of figs is %: psoralen is contained in 0.31-0.66% in the root bark and 0.22-0.49% in the stem bark. The content of bergapten in the leaves is 0.05-0.12, in the root bark 0.04-0.12. The leaves of wild figs contain 0.4-0.55 coumarin, including 0.24-0.31 bergapten. The milk juice of unripe figs contains 0.14-0.27 psoralen and 0.03-0.04 bergapten. In ripe fruits, the content of psoralen is 0.01-0.05%, while bergapten occurs in the form of traces. During the appearance of the first buds and the first leaves (April - May), the psoralene content is 0.85-0.91, and bergapten-0.29-0.31. With the initial fermentation of fresh leaves, the psoralen yield increases by 45-55%. Figs also contain a small amount of flavonoids, vitamins B1, B2, C, E, PP, tannins, alkaloids. Fig seeds contain 29.4% fat and 96.17% consist of glycerides and unsaturated acids. It has a high content of linolenic acid, namely-48.71%. The quality of fig tree is close to tung oil and can be used in the paint and varnish industry (E. A. Yarosh, 1975). In the food industry, fig fruits are consumed fresh and dried. Jam, jam, compotes are made from them. Fig puree is widely used in the manufacture of desserts in folk medicine figs are recommended for patients with malnutrition after severe illnesses, in the treatment of anemia and diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. Decoction of dried

figs on milk is considered a powerful cough remedy, and milky juice from leaves, branches and unripe fruits is used to heal wounds and remove warts and pimples Fig jam (with black tea) is used for sore throats and inflammatory diseases of the respiratory tract. Application procedure 100 g of dried figs are boiled in 2 cups of boiling water over low heat for 15 minutes, left for 2-3 hours, then filtered and consumed 2-3 times a day before meals with a strong cough. In ancient medicine, figs were used as a refreshing agent that stimulates the activity of the liver, heart and other internal organs According to Ibn Sina, figs are more nutritious than all fruits. Fresh and dried figs help with fainting (a condition of fainting associated with hypotension), open blockage of the liver and spleen, useful for the kidneys and bladder.

The milky juice of figs, when ingested, drives sand out of the kidneys, it is recommended for difficult-to-digest tumors and for accelerating the rupture of pus. The juice squeezed from its leaves removes tattoos and cures scabies. In case of inflammatory diseases of the upper respiratory tract, gargling with fig tincture is recommended. According to the descriptions of Muhammad Hussein Sherazi, figs are useful for heartburn, bronchial asthma, cough, chest pain Eating figs before meals is useful for softening the body, especially the intestines. In modern medicine, figs are recommended for diseases of the cardiovascular system, anemia, prescribed to patients with a tendency to thrombosis Figs are used to improve digestion and as a mild laxative (S. Ya. Sokolov et al., 1985). The dietary value of figs, unlike other fruits, is due to the presence of a large amount of fructose and glucose in it and their low acidity of the medium. The drug furagin was developed from fig leaves, which is used to treat vitiligo (PES) and other skin baldness

Furalene has photosensitizing properties and is not inferior in activity to ammifurine, beroxane and psoralene. The drug does not have a toxic effect. The period of accumulation of the largest amount of psoralen in fig leaves for furalen production falls on August-September, and it is then that it is harvested. The collected raw materials are dried in the shade at a temperature of 20-25 ° C.

Conclusion: Therefore, all plants storing medicinal herbs are processed according to the above method for the preparation of decoctions, teas, tinctures, liquid extracts, while it is necessary to observe all methods When using fig fruits, caution is emphasized in patients with diabetes mellitus due to the high sugar content in them.

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